

Human Security Implications of Non-Traditional Maritime Security Threats in the Western Indian Ocean

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Abstract

The Western Indian Ocean region has emerged as a dynamic maritime space characterized by evolving security challenges that extend beyond traditional state-centric threats. This research study delves into the human security implications of non-traditional maritime security threats in the Western Indian Ocean, shedding light on the multifaceted dimensions. Against the backdrop of increasing transnational crime, environmental degradation, and geopolitical tensions, this research has analysed the diverse range of non-traditional maritime security threats. Additionally, the study also investigates the role of international actors, regional organizations, and legal frameworks in addressing and mitigating these challenges, as well as their effectiveness in promoting human security. Ultimately, this research aims to inform strategies that safeguard human security in the face of evolving maritime challenges in the Western Indian Ocean.

Keywords

Human Security , of Non-Traditional Maritime , Security Threats , Western Indian Ocean

Introduction

The Western Indian Ocean region covers a sizeable maritime area that stretches from the Gulf of Aden in the north to the Mozambique Channel in the south along the eastern coast of Africa. This region includes the countries, Kenya, Comoros, Madagascar, France, Mauritius, Mozambique, Somalia, Seychelles, Tanzania and South Africa. The strategic position, abundant marine resources, and vital maritime trade routes give this area a great deal of importance. One of the most important connections between the Indian Ocean and the rest of the world is the Western Indian Ocean area. It includes important international maritime channels that support global trade and transit, such as the congested Suez Canal and the Mozambique Channel. The Western Indian Ocean is one of the regional seas designated by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), and it encompasses the western half of the Indian Ocean in a cohesive biogeographic, climatic, and socio-political zone. With exclusive economic zones (EEZs) encompassing more than 6 million km² and a total coastline of more than 15,000 km, it has a surface area of around 30 million km², or 8.1% of the world's ocean surface (UNEP/Nairobi Convention Secretariat 2009). The Western Indian Ocean region's coastal nations are significantly dependent on marine resources for both their subsistence and their economic growth. The region's economy depends heavily on the fishing industry since it creates jobs, ensures food security, and opens up export prospects. The economic development of the coastal nations is also significantly influenced by the shipping and tourism industries. There are a variety of security problems that might affect the Western Indian Ocean region. The region has traditionally been affected by conventional security issues such territory disputes and naval warfare. Threats to marine security that aren't traditional have become major problems in the Western Indian Ocean in recent years. These threats are characterised by their transnational nature, asymmetric warfare, and impact on civilian populations. Non-traditional maritime security threats in the region include piracy, illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, maritime terrorism, environmental degradation, and smuggling. These

challenges pose significant risks to the human security of coastal communities, exacerbating existing vulnerabilities and undermining sustainable development efforts. Combating these challenges necessitates regional and global cooperation as well as the implementation of effective legal frameworks and security measures.

Aim of study

The study explores non-traditional security threats in the Western Indian Ocean region, their impact on human security, and the mechanisms to counter these threats.

Review of Literature

The Western Indian Ocean area has become a breeding ground for non-conventional maritime security risks that extend beyond regular state-centric concerns. Researchers like Bueger and Stockbruegger emphasise the dynamic character of maritime security concerns, pointing out how regional stability is disrupted by piracy, maritime terrorism, and environmental degradation and how these issues need creative solutions. The emergence of non-traditional maritime threats pose a danger to the security and stability in the region. Apart from being non-military in nature, these challenges are also transnational, and neither purely domestic nor totally inter-state. (Chatterjee) The spread of illicit weapons in the region has created a highly dangerous scenario that is difficult to govern and control for any one country. (Biswas) The loss of coral reefs and increased pollution amplify vulnerabilities in coastal regions, affecting both environmental integrity and human well-being. According to research Coastal small-scale fisheries account for more than half of worldwide seafood capture, which provides food security and economic livelihood for fishermen, families, and communities, and employing up to three times as many people. (Desai and Shambaugh) Non-Traditional maritime security threats have a direct impact upon the economic security, health security, environment security, food security, personal security and human rights. In order to have a check on the rising challenges of non-traditional security threats, domestic, regional and international mechanisms are needed to be enforce so that the impact of these threats on the human security be reduced and eradicated.

Main Text**Non-Traditional Maritime Security Threats in the Western Indian Ocean**

The Western Indian Ocean region faces a variety of non-traditional maritime security threats, which go beyond conventional state-centric security issues. These threats have become important issues influencing the stability, safety, and socioeconomic growth of the area.

Maritime security has been significantly impacted by piracy in the Western Indian Ocean, notably off the coast of Somalia and the Gulf of Aden. Piracy has been a persistent threat in the Western Indian Ocean. Somalia's political unrest, poverty, poor leadership, and the ease with which guns are accessible are all factors that contribute to piracy. Commercial, fishing, and recreational boats have all been targeted by pirates who have taken control of the ships and demanded ransom. This disrupts international trade, increases the costs of insurance, and poses risks to the safety of seafarers. Although piracy has decreased in recent years due to counter-piracy efforts, such as international naval patrols, onboard security measures, international cooperation and enhanced security measures, it remains a concern requiring ongoing attention.

A serious security risk in the Western Indian Ocean is posed by the growth of maritime terrorism. Extremist organisations like Al-Shabaab and Al-Qaida have proven they are capable of carrying out operations from or at the sea. Ports, offshore platforms, ships, and other crucial maritime infrastructure are among the targets. A destroyer of US Navy was attacked by Al-Qaeda with a boat stacked with explosives when it was in the Port of Aden on 12 October 2000. Maritime terrorism threatens the stability of coastal states, disrupts maritime trade, jeopardises the safety of seafarers and undermines regional security. It is necessary to share intelligence, capacity-building efforts, improve maritime domain awareness, and implement border control strategies in order to combat maritime terrorism.

Illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing is quite prevalent in the Western Indian Ocean region which threatens the marine resources and coastal economies. Foreign vessels engage in unauthorised fishing within national waters, undermining sustainable fisheries management, underreporting catches, depleting fish stocks, the use of destructive gear and operating without licenses contribute to overfishing, depletion of fish stocks, and economic losses for coastal communities. The overall potential yearly loss to the region's potential income due to IUU fishing of shrimp and tuna was US\$142.8 million between 2015 and 2021. IUU fishing disrupts the balance of marine ecosystems in the region, which also depletes fish stocks, jeopardises food security, threatens local fishermen's livelihoods, interferes with sustainable fisheries management, and threatens to undermine local fishermen's livelihoods. In order to combat this threat, effective

monitoring and surveillance systems, stronger legal restrictions, international cooperation and capacity-building initiatives are required.

The Western Indian Ocean is used by several trafficking and smuggling networks as a transit route. Significant security issues exist in the Western Indian Ocean as a result of smuggling operations, such as drug trafficking, the smuggling of weaponry, human trafficking, and the smuggling of contraband products. In order to engage in these illegal operations, criminal networks take advantage of porous coasts and weak maritime boundaries, which feeds organised crime and undermines government. Smuggling and trafficking puts human lives at risk, compromises government, and has negative socioeconomic effects on both the country of origin and the country of destination. In order to combat smuggling and trafficking, stronger legal systems must be put in place, intelligence sharing should be increased, and collaboration between governments is necessary.

Environmental degradation in the Western Indian Ocean is an issue that is becoming worse and has serious consequences i.e. having direct human security implications. Oil spills, unlawful disposal of hazardous waste, destructive fishing methods, and the destruction of coral reefs are just a few examples of the activities that degrade marine ecosystems, reduce biodiversity, and impair the way of life for coastal populations. Food security is put at risk, tourism is affected, and natural catastrophe vulnerabilities are increased as a result of environmental degradation. Strict laws, ethical fishing methods, attempts to conserve the ocean, and the promotion of environmentally friendly policies are all necessary to mitigate environmental damage.

Implication on Human Security

There are substantial implications for human security from the non-traditional marine security risks in the Western Indian Ocean region. Human security refers to the protection and promotion of the well-being and rights of individuals, ensuring their freedom from fear and want. In the Western Indian Ocean, non-traditional maritime security risks have a substantial influence on a variety of human security-related factors.

Unlawful activities such as piracy, IUU fishing, and smuggling are having a negative upon the economic security. The disruption of maritime trade by piracy raises expenses for shipping firms, increases the cost of insurance, and ultimately impacts customers. It discourages investments, has an impact on tourism, and hinders economic development. The economic stability of coastal towns is at risk owing to the depletion of fish populations brought on by illegal fishing methods, which affects local fishermen's revenue options. Smuggling and trafficking weakens legal economies, disrupts commerce, and adds to corruption, all of which impede economic progress and development. According to the estimates by International Maritime Bureau, maritime piracy causes US\$16 billion in economic damages annually as a result of theft, ransom, delays in transportation, higher costs of insurance, and anti-piracy measures.

Food security in the area is seriously threatened by the IUU fishing and environmental damage. Coastal communities' food security is impacted by the depletion of fish populations brought on by destructive fishing methods and overfishing, which also diminish the availability of nutrient-dense seafood. This makes poverty and starvation worse in the region. Food security may be further threatened by environmental deterioration, which can impair marine ecosystems and interfere with fisheries' natural production. Examples of this include the destruction of coral reefs and pollution.

The health security of the Western Indian Ocean region is affected by various non-traditional marine security risks. Acts of piracy and maritime terrorism can result in fatalities, severe bodily harm, severe psychological harm, and other consequences that have an effect on the health and well-being of seafarers, coastal communities, and others in impacted areas. Along with this, marine ecosystems that are polluted or degraded, coastal waterways can become contaminated. This lowers the quality of the water and puts populations that depend on marine resources for food and livelihoods at risk of health problems.

The environmental security in the Western Indian Ocean region is threatened by environmental deterioration brought on by non-traditional marine security concerns. The natural equilibrium of coastal environment is impacted when coral reefs are destroyed, pollution is released into the environment, and overfishing occurs. The well-being and safety of coastal populations may be put in danger as a result of negative effects such coastal erosion, habitat loss, and greater vulnerability to natural catastrophes.

Non-traditional maritime security threats also have implications for personal security and human rights. The safety and lives of sailors, fishing communities, and residents of coastal areas are at stake due to piracy and maritime terrorism. According to ICC International Maritime Bureau, between 2018 to 2022, a total of 283 seafarers were taken as hostages, 13 were injured and 2 were killed due to piracy incidents. People are the victims of violence, exploitation, and violations of their human rights as a result of criminal activities related to smuggling, such as drug trafficking and human trafficking. Effective law enforcement, maritime combat patrols, and the protection of human rights are necessary for ensuring personal security.

Existing Human Security Mechanism

The term "human security mechanisms" refers to a broad variety of programmes, organisations, and methods used to safeguard and promotes the dignity, welfare, and rights of individuals. Beyond conventional military concerns, these mechanisms handle a variety of security-related issues, such as those with an impact on the economy, society, the environment, and politics. These includes conflict prevention and resolution, peacekeeping, humanitarian assistance, human rights protection, development assistance, environmental sustainability, and more. Human security mechanisms cover a wide range of risks, such as conflicts, natural catastrophes, poverty, sickness, and human rights violations, with the goal of creating a secure and free world for people.

1. **Regional Cooperation Initiatives:** Regional cooperation mechanisms like the Djibouti Code of Conduct and Indian Ocean Commission aim to improve collaboration among coastal states in addressing maritime security threats. These initiatives promote information sharing, joint patrols, capacity-building, and legal frameworks. Their success relies on member states' commitment, resource allocation, and agreed-upon measures.

2. **International Naval Patrols:** International coalitions like Combined Maritime Forces and European Union Naval Force deploy naval patrols in the Western Indian Ocean to combat piracy and protect commercial shipping. Their effectiveness relies on sustained presence, coordination, and adaptability to evolving threats.

3. **Legal Frameworks and Prosecution:** International legal frameworks, such as the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea and national legislation helps in addressing maritime security threats by prosecuting pirates, illegal fishing operators, and smugglers. Their effectiveness depends on their implementation, enforcement, and state capacity to investigate, prosecute, and adjudicate cases.

4. **Capacity-Building and Training:** Capacity-building programs aim to strengthen coastal states' maritime law enforcement, surveillance, and response capabilities to effectively address non-traditional maritime security threats. Their efficacy relies on sustained support, ongoing training, and skill transfer to relevant agencies and institutions.

5. **Information Sharing and Intelligence Cooperation:** Information sharing and intelligence cooperation are essential for early detection, prevention, and response to maritime security threats. Platforms like Regional Maritime Information Fusion Centre (RMIFC) Madagascar and Regional Coordination Operations Centre (RCOC) Seychelles, facilitate information exchange, relying on accurate reporting, trust, and efficient utilisation of shared information for operational purposes.

Conclusion A complex web of non-traditional maritime security threats, each have a substantial impact on human security, are present in the Western Indian Ocean region. The economic stability, food security, health, well-being, environmental sustainability, and personal safety of coastal communities are threatened by the combination of piracy, illicit fishing, maritime terrorism, environmental degradation, etc. These threats highlight the necessity of a multifaceted strategy that incorporates strong capacity-building, close regional coordination, and strict adherence to regulatory requirements. Although human security measures already in place have helped addressing non-traditional maritime security concerns, their efficacy depends on ongoing dedication, cooperation, and budget allocation. In order to mitigate these problems and build resilient communities, cooperation among coastal nations, international organisations, and non-state actors is essential.

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